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Executive Summary

This document is the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ARCFISH project funded by the national funding bodies in Norway (Research Council of Norway (RCN)), Portugal (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)), Poland (The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland (NCBR)), Denmark (Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD)) and Iceland (The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland (RANNIS)), after successful evaluation of the proposals for the 2023 First Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call. The DMP describes the data products and other digital resources that will be generated by the partners in the course of the project.

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters. New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. For example, for Disko Bay, western Greenland, ecosystem indices based on an improved ecosystem model could include monthly spatial maps of zooplankton biomass and production, benthos biomass, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Data collected around Iceland towards the Barents Sea onboard fishing vessels and in seafood processing could be implemented in the DTO to support relevant stakeholders. For the Arctic in general, potential new services could include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualisation. For cost-efficiency these services must leverage novel digital technologies such as DTOs to acquire, process, analyse and visualise heterogeneous data from a wide range of sources.

This first version of the DMP presents the plan for data management in ARCFISH six months into the project. During the project, the DMP will be updated with information about new categories of data products and other digital resources that will be generated as part of ARCFISH. This will include descriptions of metadata and data standards to be used for different data products, documentation of data processing, identification of suitable licenses, citation and acknowledgement statements, and selection of data repositories used for securing long-term storage and access. Similar consideration will be given to support FAIR handling of other resources generated by the project, such as software components, training material, presentations and publications.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1. Background.....	6
1.2. Organisation of the document	6
2. Data collection and generation.....	7
3. Documentation and metadata.....	7
4. Ethics and legal compliance	8
5. Storage and backup.....	8
6. Selection and preservation	8
7. Data sharing	9
8. Responsibilities and resources.....	9
9. References.....	9

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
ACDD	Attribute Convention for Data Discovery
AIS	Automatic Identification System
Blue-Cloud2026	A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
CF	Climate and Forecast convention
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DIF10	Directory Interchange Format version 10
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)
eCUDO	Electronic Oceanographic Data Centre (Poland)
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IFD	Innovation Fund Denmark
ILIAD	Integrated digital solution facilitates access to oceanic data and boosts decision-making
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic observation system
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISO 19115	ISO Geographic information — Metadata standard
NCBR	The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NIRD	National Infrastructure for Research Data (Norway)
NMDC	Norwegian Marine Data Centre
OceanSITES	Ocean Reference Stations (sustained observatory network)
PI	Principal Investigator
RANNIS	The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland
RCN	Research Council of Norway
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) Platform delivering new data products and services in support of sustainable Arctic Fisheries. These data products and services will be co-designed with stakeholders in the fisheries sector and used to create products such as ecosystem indices that can be applied in fisheries planning and management. Available data sources and existing gaps will be analysed to fulfil user needs and ingest relevant data into the Blue Insight DTO Platform. They include (1) oceanographic data from research vessels, autonomous mobile platforms, fixed buoys, and ships of opportunity such as e.g., fishing vessels, (2) met-ocean-ice forecasts and reanalyses from models (e.g., from CMEMS and INTAROS), (3) fisheries management data (e.g., fisheries stocks, species) from ICES and national sources, and (4) auxiliary reference data (e.g., bathymetry, economic zones, AIS data).

Based on the stakeholders needs, a use case for sustainable fisheries will be implemented using the ingested data and tools for generating customised products. The use case will address two geographic regions, the west coast of Greenland centred around the rich fishing grounds surrounding Disko Bay, and the region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and towards the Barents Sea. Using the compiled data collections and developed tools, a regional database of climate, environmental, and fisheries data will be created and made available through an open data repository to support sustainable Arctic Fisheries. This important asset will contribute to the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program by providing new data products that can be utilised in digital twin platforms to support decision-making in fisheries management.

The Blue Insight digital platform developed by Kongsberg Discovery, Norway, will be part of the Digital Twins of the Ocean (DITTO) program of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. As part of DITTO and through engagement with other running Digital Twin projects and initiatives such as EDITO, ILIAD, Blue-Cloud2026 and EOSC, ARCFISH development will follow standards for data exchange and implementation of services and tools in the EU DTO. ARCFISH will prepare training material for using the Blue Insight DTO and organise capacity building events for stakeholders and other SBE projects. Training will be organised in conjunction with project meetings and SBEP seminars. Furthermore, the regional database, developed services and tools, training and promotional material will be promoted through the iAOS portal from INTAROS, a public project website linked to relevant DTO sites, and dedicated social media channels. ARCFISH results will also be promoted through the partners extensive network within communities focused on Arctic observing and data management, digital technologies, capacity building in ocean literacy, stakeholder interactions and fisheries.

1.2. Organisation of the document

The structure of the DMP is based on the Digital Curation Centre's Data Management Plan template (DCC, 2018). Section 2 describes data repositories selected for long-term storage and access to data products generated in the project, while Section 3 provides information about the formats and metadata structures to be used. Section 4 outlines some aspects of ethical and legal compliance to fulfil the Research Council's Open Data Policy and the FAIR data principles. The three next sections describe practical aspects of data management in the project, including storage and backup (Section 5), what data will be selected for long term preservation (Section 6), and the role and responsibilities of the partners (Section 7).

2. Data collection and generation

The project will focus on utilizing existing data from open repositories and partners inventories. Expected data products include, among others, ecosystem indices for Greenlandic waters, in situ observations and derived or integrated products for the study areas, a broad range of fisheries and fishing vessel data, as well as aggregated satellite and model products. Expected software products include e.g. services for data ingestion, analysis and visualisation in the ARCFISH DTO.

Non-proprietary data and software will be posted in sustained open repositories, such as: (1) the Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC), a national e-infrastructure for marine data in Norway; (2) eCUDO ODIS, the Polish national infrastructure for storage of marine data and information; (3) Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) Database, holding data from the Greenland integrated monitoring programme; (4) Zenodo, a general-purpose open repository with long-term support from CERN, OpenAIRE and the EC. Other repositories may be considered depending e.g. on stakeholder needs.

These e-infrastructures will issue unique persistent identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) that can be included in citation statements to provide a distinctive reference to an individual resource or a collection of related resources. Data products will be stored in the sustained data infrastructures listed above, while other digital resources will be stored in a project community on Zenodo. This will ensure that both data and other digital resources will remain available for at least 10 years after the project ends. The data licence issued by the data/resource owner(s) will determine acceptable use and how the asset should be cited and acknowledged by the consumer.

3. Documentation and metadata

Standard metadata and data formats will be used to document, format, and store ARCFISH data products to make them more easily accessible to both the public (including science) and private sector. Furthermore, less efforts will be required to incorporate the products in software systems such as digital twins or user applications by means of open standard protocols. Adopting standard formats and APIs will increase interoperability and foster reusability since several mature software frameworks and tools are available and can be used as building blocks in service and system development.

For metadata and data formats the ARCFISH project will build on earlier work in e.g. INTAROS (Hamre et al., 2021), which is based on widely adopted standards such as NetCDF, CF, ACDD, and OceanSITES. Software (e.g., source code, Docker containers, pipelines) will be available with licences defining rules for use and modification. Some of such assets are expected to be restricted to protect the IPR and exploitation plans of the respective owners. Other software assets will be issued with an open-source licence allowing free use and also modifications as long as the original software developers are credited.

For datasets and products compiled from other (external) providers, we will retain the original metadata from the provider. If these metadata do not follow one of the approved standards above, we will generate a DIF 10 or ISO 19115 compliant metadata record describing the dataset or product.

4. Ethics and legal compliance

The data collected, as well as derived and estimated data products, will be managed in line with the Research Council's policy for Open Access to Research Data and the FAIR data principles. The partner generating a data product will have the Intellectual Property (IP) of it and have the right to be credited when the dataset is used. If a dataset or product is produced in collaboration between several partners, they will have joint IP to it, and users of the data shall credit all of them when using the data in line with the data owner's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) policies.

Open publishing of data from Norwegian partners will be through the Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC), from the Polish partner through eCUDO, and from the Danish partner through the GEM Database. These data infrastructures as well as Zenodo can be used by the other partners. This will ensure all datasets obtain a unique reference, a digital object identifier (DOI), for accrediting the organisation, individual employees and suppliers that have contributed to said dataset. The datasets will be prepared in a standard data format, with accompanying metadata to support discovery and reuse. Metadata will also include, among others, a citation statement and a data license regulating the future use of the data.

5. Storage and backup

Each partner is responsible for securely storing data, software assets, and other digital resources that they use or generate within the project. Appropriate backup mechanisms provided by their institution or by national or international infrastructures shall be used. Any personal data assembled e.g. in connection with training or other projects events must be handled in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), by the partner collecting these data.

6. Selection and preservation

Data products that have been quality controlled and processed to a level yielding useful information to support Arctic fisheries will be permanently stored, with references to underlying measurements ("raw data"), derived quantities or model simulations. Such ocean, marine ecosystem and sea ice products derived from observations and/or combined with satellite-based data and/or model projections, will be co-developed with users and stakeholders. The new products will be refined iteratively, and when providing useful information for supporting Arctic fisheries, they will be permanently stored. Data quality will be documented and made available together with data products, either in publications linked to or directly embedded in the metadata of the data files.

The new set of data products and other digital resources (e.g. processing and analysis tools) will be used to demonstrate to users and stakeholders in Arctic fisheries the benefits of combining data from multiple sources (e.g. in situ observations, satellite sensors, model projections, fisheries data, AIS) for integrative analysis.

7. Data sharing

Open data products and digital resources (e.g. sample services) will be shared with external users and stakeholders through the data infrastructures listed in Section 2. Customised data products for Arctic fisheries will also be shared through the ARCFISH DTO, realised by the Blue Insight digital platform.

Each data owner is responsible for registering own data products in the designated data infrastructure and other digital resources in Zenodo. NERSC will create a project community on Zenodo enabling easy access to all digital resources published by the project. NERSC maintains the iAOS portal developed in INTAROS and will support partners in registering their data products and services there to make them visible to the Arctic marine science community.

Some data products and/or other digital resources (e.g. source code, software tools, cloud services) may be shared only between project partners. This can, for instance, be due to license restrictions on parts or whole data products or software assets, or to protect the IP of partners or external parties. Such data products and other digital resources will be stored in repositories with suitable authentication and authorization mechanisms, to prohibit improper access and/or use.

8. Responsibilities and resources

The Principal Investigator (PI) of each partner is responsible for ensuring that their staff conducts data capture/gathering, processing and analysis, formatting and documentation, storage, and publication, according to the current version of the data management plan for the project. In cases where several partners collaborate on generation of products, their respective PIs shall decide which PI has the overall responsibility for managing the joint data product.

NERSC has the overall responsibility for revising the data management plan as needed, with input from all partners on their data management activities from initial planning to making their data products and other digital resources publicly available.

All partners have allocated resources in their budgets for safe and long-term storage of their digital assets.

9. References

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